

Academic Analysis on the Factors Affecting the Parent's Negative Behavior towards the Business in the Private School Management Sector

Dr. Ufuk Akbiyik

To cite this article: Collaborate, Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 66 – 86. - 0099-0001-2209-0503.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

"" • Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The magazine is published monthly.

CURRENT SCIENCE

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

A subset of parents involved in their children's education in the private sector is causing frustration for school principals. A survey conducted and distributed by Attain magazine, published by the Association of Independent Preparatory Schools (IAPS), found that "the vast majority" of principals in paid primary schools described the unrealistic demands of parents as "a vast majority". This ranked higher than paperwork, changes in government policy, and overall workload. Some parents said that they approach their children's education with the logic of "the

customer buys the product". When writing blogs, newsletters or essays, school administrators often find themselves trying to comfort overly anxious or overly ambitious parents. Independent school sectors, but most of these parents have a reasonable approach. They come from a perspective that the school knows best and tend to be supportive and understand the mutual trust connection that exists between the two parties. Besides the hasty response, she argues, close parent involvement is often a good thing. However, because fee-paying parents "make a clear commitment" to the importance of education, it is imperative that independent schools place a significant emphasis on effective communication, as he explains. It is not because people in the public sector have no ambition. But as there are fewer students in each classroom and fewer students in the private sector overall, we need to do more to be accessible. When we talk to parents, we always tell them not to call the police the first time they hear it. Horton agrees that paying parents expect a much more direct route to trainers (and indeed to managers in the hierarchy). Private schools often have smaller pastoral groups, making it easy to form intimate bonds. According to Horton, teachers need to make themselves available to parents electronically. He also warns that the emphasis on fast approaching emails has reached a point where the time it takes to reply to an email has a significant impact on how a teacher is viewed.

Keywords: *Private School Management Sector, Parent's Negative Behavior Against School, Factors Affecting Parent's Negative Behaviors Against Business*

1. Introduction

"A less qualified instructor who gets back to their students quickly can be viewed more positively than a more qualified instructor who doesn't respond to emails." Parents today set extremely lofty standards for their children. According to Horton , such demands are ways some parents react to the fact that they must make sacrifices to support their child's education. Others believe that paying is tantamount to handing over full control of their children to educators, while others devote themselves wholeheartedly to helping the school. Still others insist that the school consistently meet expectations for their children. This second scenario can be just as problematic as having an excessive amount of interference.

CURRENT SCIENCE

This ensures that instructors are not alone when addressing parents' concerns and questions. "There's a lot of interaction with parents right now and educators need to be open to seeking input." More recent perspectives highlight the importance of the education sector in planning a nation's socioeconomic growth. It does this by promoting the development of knowledge and skills that develop human abilities. More specifically, it does this by making people more confident, more aware, and more physically active. This has the effect of accelerating economic growth. It is natural for parents to want to provide their children with the best educational opportunities.

In addition to managing their child's growth and well-being, parents also have a responsibility to take care of their child's health and do whatever they can to improve it. The social, economic, and cultural aspects of their children's lives are often the primary concerns of parents. In recent years, the private education sector has managed to improve its financial situation by taking steps to ensure its sustainability. These steps include attracting sufficient funds by increasing fee collection from a small percentage to subtracting full fees. In addition, the private education sector was able to ensure its own sustainability. In addition, the private sector is becoming more important as a place for stakeholders to put their money, as it instructs young people. The study emphasized examining the greater motivation that led parents to make such a choice in terms of exploring the benefits and drawbacks of private schools. Following the analysis of the relevant literature, eight key factors that have an impact on educational outcomes have been found. These include social background and status, income level, school curriculum, school environment and facilities, school performance, location, teacher quality and distance.

The aim of this study is to explore the factors that are most important for parents when choosing a private school as an educational institution for their children. The study analyzed what prompted parents to make such a choice by exploring the strengths and shortcomings of these private schools and exploring the factors and challenges parents face when choosing which school to send their children to. This article supplies an overview of the substantial number of criteria confirmed by researchers using a range of private sector primary sources. As a result, a research based on literature review was conducted to decide the factors affecting the parents' preferences to send their children to private schools. Currently, many studies are exploring various perspectives on the subject. For example, West (2001), Bosetti (2004), Jackson, C. and Bisset, M. (2005), and

Ungerleider (2003) all conclude that a school's performance at school is important as well as its reputation. Standardized tests are crucial factors that influence parents' decisions about their children's educational environment.

2. Parents who are not satisfied with the quality of the education supplied

Van Pelt , Allison, and Allison (2007) found that demographic characteristics of parents, such as education level, are the reasons parents choose a private school for their children. This finding contradicts the findings of the earlier study. In addition, a different study by Beavis (2004) presented results on family background characteristics associated with parents choosing private schools for their children. Parents who were not satisfied with the quality of education provided in public schools often enroll their children in a private institution. In addition, there were several factors affecting the parents' decision to send their children to private schools, such as the education level of the parents, the professions of the parents, the educational environment, the teacher-student ratio, and the teacher-student ratio. Private schools often have smaller class sizes. Although there are some differences between the influencing factors, Dronkers and Peter (2003) found that the main reason for the difference between private and public schools is the environment in which students learn.

While it is reasonable to assume that these causes or variables are interrelated, the order in which they appear in the list of priorities and the priority hierarchy may differ depending on the effects selected. Alternative education settings and private schools Avram , S., and Dronkers , J. (2010) concluded that the characteristics of private schools, often chosen rather than public schools, have the potential to be a model for student development. This may be a result of the proliferation of prestigious private schools originally designed to cater to the educational needs of wealthy families and bright students . Private schools may be rare, but they are by no means fundamentally different from public institutions. The fact that private schools are more autonomous and able to live on their own is one of the most important advantages that distinguish them from public schools. Because of the strict admissions standards imposed by some institutions that encourage parents to view the process of enrolling their child as a personal challenge, parents are inspired to choose a

CURRENT SCIENCE

school for their child. According to Previous Researchers' Opinions on Factors Affecting West (2001), Bosetti (2004), Jackson, C., and Bisset , M. (2005) Ungerleider (2003), found that the reputation of the school is important as well as its performance. Standardized tests are crucial factors parents should consider when making school choices. According to Van Pelt , Allison, and Allison (2007), demographic characteristics of parents, such as education level, are the reasons for parents to choose a private school for their children. According to Beavis (2004), results on family history aspects associated with parents choosing private schools have been reported.

Parents who are not satisfied with the quality of education provided in public schools prefer to enroll their children in private schools. According to Dronkers and Peter (2003), the main reason for the difference between public and private schools is the atmosphere of the relevant institutions. Noor Allie Yaacob et al. / Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 153 (2014) 242 – 253 245 Lutz 1996 and Godwin , Kemerer et al. 1998; and McEwan 2001, the peer group has the capacity to increase or hinder achievement. This is something that can be affected. In addition, these researchers concluded that two of the most crucial factors to consider when choosing a private school are the structure of the school, as well as the financial situation of the parents.

Coleman , Hoffer, and co-authors (1982), Greeley (1982), Alexander and Pallas (1983), Falsey and Heyns (1984), Coleman and Hoffer (1987), Langout and Léger (two thousand), and Dronkers and Robert (2008) concluded that while students attending private schools often come from higher income families with better education and cultural resources, these families place higher expectations on their children . Despite this fact, Noell's 1982 research showed that the private school sector offers less accommodation for students with physical disabilities or other special educational needs (Parry 1996).

3. Parents' Participation in Their Children's Education Process

When it comes to their child's education, it is normal for parents to want the best for their children. This includes the obligation of parents to protect and promote the health, development, and well-being of their children in the best interests of their children. Parents are allowed to express their

CURRENT SCIENCE

opinions about the educational institution they have chosen for their child and their choice is considered (Scottish Executive , 2006). They can rely on their own personal experience to instruct their children, allowing better competition between students and schools than in a typical school system. Therefore, the types of parent involvement that involve parents directly working with their children in various educational tasks at home are the most successful forms of parent involvement (Michigan Department of Education , 2001). Mandatory parent involvement results in a cost-benefit analysis. If parents are concerned with their child's education, this should lead to more success for their children. On the other hand, parents who cannot or do not want to take part in their children's education are forced to limit their school choices to institutions that do not require parental participation (Van Dunk E. et.al , 1998).

Factors that play a role in the decision-making process of parents when choosing a private school for their children

Social History and the Present Situation According to Catsambis (1998), indicators of social background include the composition of parents' education, employment, income, choice of family property, and socioeconomic status, such as race or ethnicity.

Also, indicators of social background include what a family has. Furthermore, this highlights the importance of parents' respective employment status. According to Rehman, Khan, Triq, and Tasleem (2010), a higher status of parents' professional prestige therefore means a higher choice for their children to choose private school over public school. This is the conclusion that can be drawn from the findings of the study. Because of this situation, parents are satisfied with the school they have chosen for their children according to their preferences. In addition, parents consider several other key factors, such as the number of members in the family, the level of education the parents receive, the amount of money parents have, and the qualifications of school staff. In addition, wealth differences based on race and ethnicity are a contributing factor in a wide range of special education participation rates (Fairlie , 2006). The increasing availability of private school vouchers targeting low-income families in low-income, high-minority school districts has made it possible for more parents to send their children to private schools (Goldring and Rowley , 2006). According to the findings of this study, there is social class stratification as parents who

have access to more information and wider social networks are more likely to take part in the decision-making process.

inclusion of monetary contributions in school quality assurance , parents' annual income becomes a crucial factor influencing the choices they make about their children's education (Rehman et al., 2010). There are some instances where parents of moderate incomes and better educational backgrounds go to great lengths to ensure their child is admitted to the most prestigious private school possible. Noor Allie Yaacob et al. / Procedia - Social and behavioral Sciences 153 (2014) 242 – 253 According to Dronkers J. & S. Avram (2010), he argues that wealthy families are student success in terms of education levels and professional prestige . School Curriculum It is possible that the course outlines offered by the public school and the private school are different. Most parents choose to enroll their children in private schools that adhere to a particular religious ideology. Van Pelt et al. (2007), parents who choose schools with a religious definition are interested in the development of their children's morals, values, religion, family, and characters. However, Wilkinson et al. (2004) noted that different religious schools place different amounts of emphasis on different degrees of religious factors that are incompatible with each other. Although religion is an important consideration, the weight a family or set of parent's places on it can vary from situation to situation and from family to family when making school choices.

4. School Facilities and Surroundings

According to Smith (two thousand), school is defined as the provision of school buildings in a well-located place, consisting of the environment and opportunities supported students to focus and study. A school in general consists of a supply of these school structures. It is a site that turns complex structure into reality to impress people in terms of social perspective, school management, school organization and class distribution, quality, and effectiveness of instructors. As a result, school is not just a place that focuses on academic achievement; rather, it is an institution that focuses on the personal and social development elements of people. As a result, a school should provide its students with factors such as convenience, safety, and attractiveness. The atmosphere of the educational institution has a significant impact on the quality of the education provided (

CURRENT SCIENCE

Rehman et al ., 2010). It is possible to say that several factors are effective in the preferences of parents about the schools their children attend. These factors include the education level of the parents, the profession of the parents, the size of the classes and the student-teacher ratio. On the other hand, the condition of the school's facilities may also affect the academic achievement of children. Often, private schools conduct development by constructing new buildings or renovating existing structures to better meet teaching needs. According to Peterson and Llaudet (2006), researchers found that schools' facilities and resources had negligible effect on students' academic achievement. x Performances at School There is an undeniable connection between the success level of a school and the atmosphere of the school. According to Berry (2002), the most crucial factor deciding the quality of the overall academic performance of an educational institution is the quality of the school environment. The academic success of a private school is a crucial factor in deciding whether parents choose to enroll their children there. According to the findings of a study conducted by NCES, the academic achievement of students attending private schools was higher than students attending public schools (Peterson & Llaudet , 2006). It can be attributed to two main factors. Peterson and Llaudet (2006) concluded that there is inconsistency in the classification of student characteristics in different domains, as well as including student characteristics sensitive to the influence of schools. x Positioning Comparing how popular a school is can be explained, at least in part, by the geographic location of the area and the degree to which there is a healthy balance between supply and demand for the school. . According to Flatley (2001), the settlement planning of schools is primarily based on expected changes in the demographic field. Although the building history of the schools and school closure policies also have an impact, the settlement planning of the schools is primarily the expected changes in the demographic field. When it came time for parents to choose a school, another factor considered was the location of the school. This means that the school's environment must be easily accessible.

Bernal (2005), some subgroups of middle-class families do not try to enroll their children in the nearest higher education institution. They gave some thought to the possibility that the school closest to their home might not be the most suitable educational institution for their children. 4. Methodology Research methodologies involve the use of data from both primary and secondary

sources. Primary sources are defined only as those obtained from direct data collection through methods such as survey questionnaires and interview sessions.

5. Descriptive Analysis

For this research, it is important to explore what matters most to parents when deciding which private schools are best for their children. However, due to the limitations of the scope survey, length of time, coordination, and mobility, only the first four criteria chosen by parents will be examined in depth here. According to the findings of the survey, most parents give more priority to the importance of the curriculum offered by private schools when choosing a private education institution. Although their school is a typical private school, one of the most obvious explanations for this behavior is that parents want their children to attend private schools that incorporate religious education into the curriculum.

To this day, almost no research has been conducted to investigate whether students are supported or satisfied by their school during challenging times. Using data from the COVID-19 survey of the German National Education Panel Study, we found the main determinants of parents' impressions of school support during the national quarantine in Germany in spring 2020. Broadly speaking, the concept describes a situation in which parents are satisfied either with the way schools manage their children's education or with the more typical characteristics and performance of schools, such as the quality of school infrastructures and the quality of schools (Friedman et al., 2006). There is no accepted definition of parental satisfaction with a child's educational institution, and research on the subject requires many different approaches (Mossi et al., 2019: 1f). Although effective parent-school cooperation and the feeling of mutual support are always important for students' educational outcomes (Dusi 2012: 20ff), students are particularly at risk in such situations. Consequently, one of the characteristics that can be used to assess the quality of a school is whether it can effectively organize and distribute learning materials that are both supportive and effective (Giovannella et al., 2020).

CURRENT SCIENCE

This will allow both children and their parents to evaluate the material and understand it as much as possible. Consequently, the profound sense of school support by overworked parents during school quarantine can serve as a key criterion for deciding the quality of the school. In addition to traditional indicators, the degree to which parents' express satisfaction with their child's educational environment is a factor that can be considered in assessing the broader social relevance of school performance (Charbonneau et al., 2012).

Parents' level of satisfaction with their children's school has been found to be significantly correlated with formal school performance measures such as school characteristics and students' performance (ebd .). To our knowledge, only very few studies have been conducted on parental satisfaction in relation to the unique circumstances brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic. Much of this research has focused on a descriptive description of the current situation (Andresen et al., 2020; Anger et al., 2020; Huebner et al., 2020; Wildemann and Hosenfeld 2020; Thorell et al., 2021). In addition, not much research has been done on parents' satisfaction with the education system in Germany, and studies have focused primarily on parents of young children (Cryer et al ., 2002).

To date, no research has been conducted to explore the factors parents use to predict how their children will feel about their school if these children are part of the adolescent cohort. However, knowledge of parents' satisfaction with their child's school is also important for older children. This is because an emotionally stable social environment is necessary for a young person's maturation, particularly during the formative years of adolescence (Perry et al., 1993). Earlier research has shown that parents continue to play a key role in their child's development during the teenage years, particularly in the form of role modeling and speaking (Behnke et al., 2004). The extent to which parents are satisfied with their children's educational environment is an indicator of the quality of interaction between family and school, which is linked to the educational growth of students (Khajehpour and Ghazvini 2011; Charbonneau et al., 2012: 60f). Also, from a financial perspective, parents are considered the primary consumers of schools. Schools function as institutions within the education market and it is their duty to meet the needs of the people who use their services, also known as customers (Matland 1995; Fend 2008: 109ff). Since parents are one of the important user groups, the degree to which schools can keep and show high quality

levels should be especially important for these institutions (Charbonneau et al., 2012; Peters 2015: 342f). During the extraordinary time when schools are quarantined due to the COVID-19 pandemic , this study should contribute to increasing parents' knowledge of the level of enjoyment they feel about their children's educational experiences .

Status of the research Parents has a key role in their children's education as they are both the end users of their children's education and the primary educators of their own children (Fend 2000: 66f; Fend 2008: 109ff). However, most of the studies on school satisfaction focus their attention on student satisfaction rather than parents (Okun et al., 1990; Zullig et al., 2011; Casas et al., 2013; Weber and Huebner 2015; Arciuli). et al., 2019; Arciuli and Emerson 2020). In most cases, when researchers investigate parental satisfaction, they focus on parents of younger age groups, kindergarten, or primary school children (Ulrey et al., 1982; Griffith 2000; Cryer et al., 2002; Bailey et al., 2003; Thompson 2003; Fantuzzo et al., 2006). ; Bassok et al., 2018). In general, families of older children report lower levels of satisfaction with their children's school than families of younger students (Thompson 2003: 280f; Fantuzzo et al., 2006). This finding may suggest that parents of older children have higher educational expectations than parents of younger children (Stull 2013). Most studies assess satisfaction using tools developed for broader purposes; It has not been systematically shown that the psychometric qualities of these tools are suitable for measuring customer satisfaction of school users (Mossi et al., 2019: 2). Therefore, it is difficult to compare studies due to variable measures of parental satisfaction with educational institution (Fantuzzo et al., 2006: 144; Mossi et al., 2019). In general, important determinants of parents' satisfaction with adolescents' schooling are not clear at all.

6. Learning Processes During Education

There are some illustrative reports on learning processes during homeschooling (Andresen et al. , 2020; Andrew et al., 2020; Attig et al., 2020; Garbe et al., 2020; Parczewska 2020; Wildemann and Hosenfeld 2020; Woßmann et al., 2020). ; Zhao et al., 2020).

CURRENT SCIENCE

A similar pattern can be seen for satisfaction with schools' knowledge of the current situation (Andresen et al., 2020: 17), showing the level of satisfaction parents experience when their child is studying at school. The home is affected by many factors. Attig et al. (2020), the level of parental satisfaction with the information provided by the school depends on the type of secondary school the children attend, and the satisfaction levels in non-academic schools are higher than in non-academic schools (Atig et al. , 2020: 4). It is interesting to note that there is a unique link between parental happiness and the learning outcomes that parents think their children achieve (Atig et al., 2020). More than half of parents dissatisfied with school aid claimed that their children learned less during homeschooling, but only 11% of more satisfied parents received comparable learning feedback from their children (Atig et al., 2020). : 6ff).

On the other hand, it is still not entirely clear whether such variations in taste are significant. Prior research before homeschooling became popular because of COVID-19 found that the level of parental satisfaction was significantly influenced by several factors, including characteristics of both parents and children (Fantuzzo et al ., 2006; Friedman et al., 2006) and programs and policies implemented by schools (Bailey et al., 2003; Bassok et al., 2018; Perry et al., 2020). Collaboration between family and school has been shown to be an indicator of children's cognitive outcomes (Tuck 1995; Smit et al., 2007; Sheridan et al., 2016) and a vital part of parents' level of enjoyment (Tuck 1995; Smit et al., 2007, Christenson 2003).). According to Hughes and Kwok (2007), a high-quality parent-teacher connection was strongly (indirectly) associated with excellent academic achievement, which in turn affected the level of enjoyment experienced by parents (Tuck 1995). Tuck (1995) conducted research on various aspects of parental happiness in the United States, primarily based on descriptive statistics.

discovered a significant link between parental happiness and a variety of school factors, including the quality of teaching staff, the school environment, academic programs, social development opportunities, and extracurricular activities .

To understand why parents are satisfied with their children's schools, this research uses two different theoretical perspectives. To begin with, the level of customer satisfaction in the education market can be explained from an economic perspective (Matland 1995; Fend 2008: 109ff).

CURRENT SCIENCE

Currently, schools are increasingly recognized as institutions of the education market. Therefore, unlike other educational institutions, they are burdened by the need to meet the needs of their users or customers, as well as to succeed (Bejou 2012). The economic approach places more emphasis on the concept of a competitive education market, whose primary emphasis is on the services that schools must provide to their customers (Matland 1995). Parental satisfaction is a reliable indicator of various quality indicators of schools (Charbonneau et al ., 2012: 61). Since parents are notable members of the school community, educational institutions need to place a strong emphasis on ensuring that parents are happy to keep an elevated level of quality (Wilson 2009: 574f; Charbonneau et al., 2012; Peters 2015: 342f).

However, there are various approaches that schools can use to meet the needs of their students (Bejou 2012: 60). Due to the school lockout in Germany in the spring of 2020, the education market is now in a tricky situation, and short-term significant changes in schooling have made it difficult for schools to meet the demands of their students (Giovannella et al. al ., 2020; Verma , 2020).

Due to the lack of sufficient time for adequate preparation, schools and teachers have had to provide students and their families with new opportunities to exchange information about effective materials for distance learning, online teaching formats, and home learning processes (Konig et al ., 2020; Bubb and Jones, 2020). Despite this, many German schools were already behind in the transition to digitization before the school restriction began (Fraillon et al., 2019: 37f; Konig et al., 2020: 610f).

There are seven indicators that contribute to parents' feelings of the level of involvement their children's teachers show: professionalism, enjoyment of learning, boring responsibility, respect for children, importance of the teacher, teachers' personal knowledge of students, and parents' attitude. ability to trust teachers .

Because the teacher is the primary and, in many cases, the only interaction between home and school, the teacher's actions may be the first thing that comes to mind when parents are asked about their level of satisfaction with the school. So, an earlier study of African American parents showed the same result: parents' attitudes towards teachers were the strongest indicators of how they rated public schools (Thompson 2003). Also, Friedman et al. (2007) found that the way schools and

CURRENT SCIENCE

teachers communicate with parents about their children's academic development accounted for 41% of the variation in parent-reported satisfaction levels. Our findings imply that parents' prior knowledge of teachers plays a role in shaping their perspectives during school lockdown. This shows that although parental satisfaction is multidimensional (Friedman et al., 2007), this structure appears stable and is not only affected by time-specific aspects (even in a very unusual event, for example). They compete with other private schools for students, by Davies and Quirke (2005). Private schools, like businesses, can change to better serve the needs of their target audiences to stay competitive.

This level of sensitivity is not always present in public schools; this is something to consider when assessing the influence of parents on curriculum creation in private schools.

This choice of funding is accompanied by an increased level of expectation about the impact it will have on choices about education. Families whose children attend private schools have the financial means to send them to a school outside the public sector. Therefore, they think that they have the right to analyze and evaluate the quality of the product they buy for their children. As a result, parents choose a school for their child that either fits the parent's educational needs or their child's educational needs. Often, parents choose a school because the mission or curriculum "addresses their expectations of their children, including their willingness to study school topics that are closely related to current academic disciplines." (Pinar, 2004, p. 228).

This motive creates a unique tension between parents and schools over conversations about the curriculum and affects school culture. This tension stems from parents wanting the best for their children.

7. Conclusion

Still, many parents may feel that due to the content of the curriculum, they cannot help their children in the areas covered at the upper levels of school. Also, due to their work and other personal obligations, parents have little time to devote to helping their children with their homework. According to Mboi and Nyambedha (2013), it is alleged that the decisions about the

implementation of special education in schools are taken at the meetings of the Parent Teachers Association (PTA), which students are not allowed to attend.

As a result, the attitudes of parents whose children go to private teaching institutions and those who do not are positive and comparable in all aspects. As a result of this finding, the second null hypothesis was accepted, and it was concluded that the judgments of the two groups about the value of tutoring were statistically independent from each other. If an alternative assessment method is used, the syndrome of trust in educational opportunities by those in the role of stakeholder will decrease and as a result, implementation will inevitably end. Considering that some parents prefer private tutoring, especially as an intensive parenting method, other than academic purposes, consultation meetings should be held to advise these parents on the need for bonding with their families.

8. References

- Alexander, KL and AM Pallas (1983). Private Schools and public Policy : New Evidence on Cognitive Achievement in Public and Private Schools. *Sociology of Education* 56(4): 170-182.
- Anders, Y. , Rossbach , H.-G., Weinert , S., Ebert, S., Kuger , S., Lehrl , S., et al. (2012). Home and Preschool Learning Environments and their Relationship to the Development of Early Numeracy skills _ *Early Child. Res . Q.* 27 (2), 231–244. doi:10.1016/j.ecresq.2011.08.003
- Andresen , S. , Lips , A., Möller , R., Rusack , T., Schröer , W., Thomas, S., et al. (2020). Kinder, Eltern and ihre Erfahrungen Während der Corona - Pandemic . Erste Ergebnisse der bundesweiten studio KiCo . Hildesheim : Universtitätsverlag Hildesheim _
- Andrew, A. , Cattan , S., Costa-Dias , M., Farquharson , C., Kraftman , L., Krutikova , S., et al. (2020). learning during the lockdown . Real-Time Data on Children's experience during home Learning. IFS Briefing

- NoteBN288 . Institute for fiscal Studies .
- Angelic , M. , and Profeta , P. (2020). Smart-Working : Work Flexibility without ConstraintsConstraints (CESifo working Paper No. 8165). Munich : Munich society for the Promotion of Economics research .
- Anger , S. , Dietrich , H., Patzina , A., Sandner , M., Lerche , A., Bernhard, S., et al. (2020). School Closings during the COVID-19 Pandemic . Findings from German High School Students . Hg. V. Iab -forum ., Online verfügbar un . Available at: <https://www.iab-forum.de/en/school-closings-during-the-covid-19-pandemic-findings-from-ger>.
- Arciuli , J. , and Emerson, E. (2020). Type of Disability, Gender , and Age Affect School Satisfaction : Findings from the UK Millennium Cohort study _ Br . J Educ . psycho _ 90 (30), pp. 870–885. doi:10.1111/bjep.12344)
- Arciuli , J. , Emerson, E., and Llewellyn , G. (2019). Adolescents ' Self-Report of School Satisfaction : The interaction between Disability and Gender . sch . psycho _ 34 (2), 148–158. doi:10.1037/spq0000275
- Attig , M. , Walter , I., and Nusser , L. (2020), Zufriedenheit in unruhigen zeitten _ Welche Rolle die communication zwischen Eltern and Schulen während der Schulschliessungen gespielt hat. Einschätzung von Eltern zur Unterstützung durch die Schule und zum Lernerfolg ihrer Kinder während des Lockdowns , 4. Bamberg : Leibniz- Institut for Bildungsverlaufe eV . (NEPS Corona & Bildung .
- Bailey , D. , Scarborough , A., and Hebbeler , K. (2003), Families ' First Experiences with early Intervention . national early Intervention longitudinal study _ NEILS DataReport. Menlo Park: SRI International.
- Bassok , D. , Markowitz , AJ, Player, D., and Zagardo , M. (2018). are Parents ' Ratings and Satisfaction with preschools Related to Program Features ?. (“Are Parents’ Ratings and Satisfaction With Preschools Related to ...”) AERA Open 4 (1), p.

233285841875995-17.

doi:10.1177/2332858418759954

verfugbar

un

doi:10.1177/0739986303262329

Beauducel , A. , and Wittmann , WW (2005).
simulation Study on Fit Indexes in
CFA Based on Data with lightly
Distorted Simple Structure . struct _
Equation Model. A Multidisciplinary
J. 12 (1), pp. 41-75.
doi:10.1207/s15328007sem1201_thr
ee

Beavis , A. (2004). Why parents choose
private or public school . Australian
Council for educational Research
(ACER). Retrieved from
<http://www.smh.com.au/articles/2004/08/17/1092508439581.html>

Beck, D.E. , Maranto , R., and Lo , W.-J.
(2014). Determinants of Students and
parent Satisfaction at a Cyber Charter
School. J Educ . Res . 107 (3), pp.
209-216.
doi:10.1080/00220671.2013.807494

Behnke , A.O. , Piercy , KW, and Diversi ,
M. (2004). educational and
Occupational Aspirations of Latino
Youth and their parent . Hispanic J.
Behav . sci . 26, pp. 16-35. online

Bejou , A. (2012). customers Relationship
Management, Exit -Voice- Loyalty ,
and Satisfaction : The Case of Public
Schools. J. Relationship Marketing
11 (2), 57-71.
doi:10.1080/15332667.2012.686386

Berry M. A. (2002). Healthy School
Environment And enhanced
educational Performance: The Case
Of Charles Young Elementary School
Washington, DC, The carpet, and rug
Institute

Bosetti , L. (2004). Determinants of school
choice : Understanding how parents
choose elementary school schools in
Alberta. Journal of Education Policy ,
19(4), 387-405.

Brehm , WC & Silova , I. (2014). hidden
privatization of public Education in
Cambodia : Equity Implication of
Private tutoring , Journal for
educational research online 6(1), 94-
116.

Catsambis S. (1998), Expanding Knowledge
of Parental Involvement Of

- secondary Education : Effects On High School Academic Success , Queens college .
- Coleman , JS, and T. Hoffer (1987). public and Private High Schools.The Impact of Communities.New York, Basic Books .
- Coleman , J. S. , T. Hoffer , et al. (1982). High School Achievement . Public , Catholic and Private Schools Compared . New York, Basic Books
- Dang, H. & Rogers, H. (2008). How to interpret the growing Phenomenon of Private Tutoring : Human Capital Deepening , Inequality Increasing , or Waste of Resources ? (World Bank Policy research working Paper 4530).
- Davies , S. , & Aurini , J (2006). the franchise of private tutoring . a view from Canada _ Phi Delta kappan , 88(2), pp123-128.
- Dronkers J. & S. Avram , (2010). Social Class Dimensions in the Selection of a Private School: A Cross- National Analysis Using PISA. educational research and Evaluation . pp . 4-5.
- Dronkers , J. and P. Robert (2008). Differences in Scholastic Achievement of Public , Private Government-Dependent and private Independent Schools.A Cross-National Analysis . educational Policy 22(4): 541-577.
- Fairlie RW (2006), Racial segregation and the Private / Public School Choice , University of California, Santa Cruz.
- Falsey , B., and B. Heyns (1984). the College Channel: Private and Public Schools Reconsidered . Socio logy of Education 57(2): 111-122.
- Flatley J. , et al. (2001), Parents ' Experiences of the Process of Choosing a Secondary School, Research Report, Department for Education and Skills ,
- Godwin , K. , F. Kemerer , et al. (1998). Liberal Equity in Education : A Comparison of Choice Options . social Science Quarterly 79(3): 502-522.
- Goldring E and Rowley KJ(2006), Parent Preferences and parent Choices : The Public-Private Decision About School Choice :

- Greeley , AM (1982). Catholic High Schools and minority students. New Brunswick , Transaction Books .
- Ho , NH (2010) .Hong Kong shadows Education . The Hong Kong Anthropologist , Volume 4, 2010.
- Jackson, C. and Bisset , M. (2005) Gender and school choice : factors influence parents when choosing single-sex or co-educational independent school for their children. Cambridge Journal of Education , 35 (2). pp . 195-211. ISSN 1469-3577
- KSSHA, (2012).Ban on holiday tuition : the pros and cons of the extra push for better grades in education . National Conference on August 15, 2012.
- Langouët , G. and A. Léger (two thousand). " public and private schooling in France: an investigation into family choice ." Journal of Education Policy 15(1): 41-49.
- Lutz , S. (1996)." The Impact of School Choice in the United States and the Netherlands on Ethnic segregation and equal educational Opportunity ."
- Equity & Excellence in Education 29(3): 48-54.
- Macdonald , JB (1977, December). Interview conducted by Ruth Fairfield at the University of North Carolina at Greensboro .
- Makworo , GW (2012).How can teachers teach effectively without extra tuition ? (Unpublished term paper , Kenyatta University).
- Marshall, J.D. , Sears , JT, Allen, LA, Roberts, P, & Schubert, W. (2007). turning points in curriculum : A contemporary American memoir . (2nd ed.). upper saddle River , NJ: Prentice hall .
- Martinez, V. J. , Godwin , RK, Kemerer , FR, & Perna , L. (1995). the consequences of school choice : Who leaves and who stay in the inner city _ social Science Quarterly , 76(3), 485-501.
- Mboi , PA & Nyambedha , EO (2013). Implications of extras tuition in primary school on pupils' social life in Kisumu Municipality , Western Kenya. ("EFFECTS OF GENDER ON THE ACADEMIC

- PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ... - SFJESGS”) International journal of education & Research , Vol , 1.No11 (pg6-7).
- McEwan , PJ (2001). the Effectiveness of Public , Catholic , and Non-Religious Private Schools in Chile's voucher System , Education Economics 9(2): 103-128.
- McGregor, D. (1960). the human side of enterprise . New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Meier , D. (two thousand). Will standards save public education ? Boston, MA: Beacon Press .
- Meier , D. (2002). Of school we trust : Creating communities of learning in an era of testing and standardization . Boston, MA: Beacon Press .
- Merriam , SB (1998). Qualitative research and case study applications in education : Revised and expanded from case study research in education . San Francisco: Jossey-Bass .
- Mertens , DM (2005). research and evaluation in education and psychology : Integrating diversity with quantitative , qualitative , and mixed methods (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks , CA: Sage Publications.
- Michigan Department of Education , 2001. OECD (Organization for Economic co-operation and Development), School Factors Related to quality and Equity ,(2005).
- Nafula , N.N. (2002). Achieving a sustainability universal primary Education through debt _ (Unpublished PHD. thesis)
- national research and Development Center on School Choice , Competition , and Achievement , 2006.
- Nzomo , J. , kariuki , M. & Guantai , L. (2001). the Quality of Primary Education : Some policy Suggestion based on a survey of schools -Kenya. SACMEQ Policy Research Report No.6. Paris: UNESCO International Institute for Educational Planning.
- Stevenson, D. & Baker, D. (1992). shadow education and allocation in formal schooling : transition to university in Japan. American Journal of sociology , 97(6), 1639-57.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Tansel, A. & Bircan, F. (2006). “ Demand for Education in Turkey : A Tobit Analysis of Private tutoring Expenditures ”. Economics of Education _ Review , 25(3):303-313.

UNESCO.(1960).Conference of ministers of Africa member States on Development of Education in Africa .